

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 19

Rev. Dr. Michael Harvey Koplitz

The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 19:0 For the choir director. A Psalm of David.</p>	<p>Psa. 19:1 לַמְנַצֵּחַ מִזְמוֹר</p>
<p>Psa. 19:1 The ^aheavens are telling of the glory of God;</p>	<p>לְדָוָד : ² הַשָּׁמַיִם מְסַפְּרִים</p>
<p>And their ^bexpanse is declaring the work of His hands.</p>	<p>כְּבוֹד-אֱלֹהִים וְמַעֲשֵׂה יָדָיו</p>
<p>² Day to ^aday pours forth speech, And ^bnight to night reveals</p>	<p>מִגִּיד הַרְקִיעַ : ³ יוֹם לְיוֹם</p>
<p>knowledge.</p>	<p>וַיָּבֵיעַ אָמַר וּלְיָלֵה לְלַיְלָה</p>
<p>³ There is no speech, nor are there words;</p>	<p>יְתוּהָ-דָעַת : ⁴ אֵין-אָמַר</p>
<p>Their voice is not heard.</p>	<p>וְאֵין דְּבָרִים בְּלִי נִשְׁמָע</p>
<p>⁴ Their ^{1a}line has gone out through all the earth,</p>	<p>קוֹלָם : ⁵ בְּכָל-הָאָרֶץ וַיֵּצֵא</p>
<p>And their utterances to the end of the world.</p>	<p>קוֹלָם וּבִקְצֵה תֵּבֵל מִלִּיהֶם</p>
<p>In them He has ^bplaced a tent for the sun,</p>	<p>לְשִׁמְשׁ שָׁם-אָהֵל בָּהֶם : ⁶</p>
<p>⁵ Which is as a bridegroom coming out of his chamber;</p>	<p>וְהוּא בִּחְתָּן יֵצֵא מִחַפְּתוֹ</p>
<p>It rejoices as a strong man to run his course.</p>	<p>וְשִׂישׁ כְּגִבּוֹר לָרוּץ אֶרֶח : ⁷</p>
<p>⁶ Its ^arising is from ¹one end of the heavens,</p>	<p>מִקְצֵה הַשָּׁמַיִם אֲמוּצָאוֹ</p>
<p>And its circuit to the ²other end of them;</p>	<p>וּתְקוּפָתוֹ עַל-קְצוֹתָם וְאֵין</p>
<p>And there is nothing hidden from its heat.</p>	<p>נִסְתָּר מִחַמָּתוֹ : ⁸ תֹּרֶת</p>
<p>Psa. 19:7 ^aThe law of the LORD is</p>	<p>יְהוָה הַמִּימָה מְשִׁיבַת נֶפֶשׁ</p>
<p>^{1b}perfect, ^crestoring the soul;</p>	<p>עֲרוֹת יְהוָה נְאֻמָּנָה מִחַפְּימָה</p>
<p>The testimony of the LORD is ^dsure, making ^ewise the simple.</p>	<p>פִּתִּי : ⁹ פִּקּוּדֵי יְהוָה יִשְׂרִים</p>
<p>⁸ The precepts of the LORD are ^aright, ^brejoicing the heart;</p>	<p>מְשִׁיחֵי-לֵב מִצְוֹת יְהוָה</p>
<p></p>	<p>בָּרָה מֵאִירַת עֵינָיִם : ¹⁰</p>

The commandment of the LORD is pure, ^denlightening the eyes.

⁹ The fear of the LORD is clean, enduring forever;

The judgments of the LORD are ^atrue; they are ^brighteous altogether.

¹⁰ They are more desirable than ^agold, yes, than much fine gold;

^bSweeter also than honey and the drippings of the honeycomb.

¹¹ Moreover, by them ^aYour servant is warned;

In keeping them there is great ^breward.

¹² Who can ^adiscern *his* errors?

^bAcquit me of ^chidden *faults*.

¹³ Also keep back Your servant ^afrom presumptuous *sins*;

Let them not ^brule over me;

Then I will be ¹⁴blameless,

And I shall be acquitted of ^dgreat transgression.

¹⁴ Let the words of my mouth and ^athe meditation of my heart

Be acceptable in Your sight,

O LORD, ^bmy rock and my

^cRedeemer.

יִרְאַת יְהוָה אִטְהוֹרָה עוֹמְדָת

לְעֵד מִשְׁפָּטֵי-יְהוָה אֱמִת

צְדָקוֹ יִתְדוֹ : ¹¹ הַנִּחְמָדִים

מִזָּהָב וּמִפָּז רַב וּמִתִּיקִים

מִדְּבַשׁ וְנֹפֶת צוּפִים : ¹² גַּם-

עֲבֹדָה נִזְתָּר בָּהֶם בְּשִׁמְרָם

עֲקֹב רַב : ¹³ שְׁגִיאוֹת מִי-

יִבִּין מִנְסֻתָרוֹת נִקְנִי : ¹⁴ גַּם

מִזִּידִים אֲחֻשֶׁה עֲבֹדָה אֶל-

יִמְשְׁלוּ-בִי אִזְ אֵיתָם וְנִקְיִתִי

מִפֶּשַׁע רַב : ¹⁵ יִהְיוּ לְרִצּוֹן |

אִמְרֵי-פִי וְהִגִּינוּ לִבִּי לְפָנֶיךָ

יְהוָה צוּרִי וְגֹאֲלִי :

References

<p>Psalm 19:1 ^aPs 8:1; 50:6; Rom 1:19, 20 ^bGen 1:6, 7</p> <p>Psalm 19:2 ^aPs 74:16 ^bPs 139:12</p> <p>Psalm 19:4 ¹Another reading is <i>sound</i> ^aRom 10:18 ^bPs 104:2</p> <p>Psalm 19:6 ¹Lit <i>the</i> ²Lit <i>the ends</i> ^aPs 113:3; Eccl 1:5</p> <p>Psalm 19:7 ¹i.e. blameless ^aPs 111:7 ^bPs 119:160 ^cPs 23:3 ^dPs 93:5 ^ePs 119:98-100</p> <p>Psalm 19:8 ^aPs 119:128 ^bPs 119:14 ^cPs 12:6 ^dPs 36:9</p> <p>Psalm 19:9 ^aPs 119:142 ^bPs 119:138</p>	<p>Psalm 19:10 ^aPs 119:72, 127 ^bPs 119:103</p> <p>Psalm 19:11 ^aPs 17:4 ^bPs 24:5, 6; Prov 29:18</p> <p>Psalm 19:12 ^aPs 40:12; 139:6 ^bPs 51:1, 2 ^cPs 90:8; 139:23, 24</p> <p>Psalm 19:13 ¹Lit <i>complete</i> ^aNum 15:30 ^bPs 119:133 ^cPs 18:32 ^dPs 25:11</p> <p>Psalm 19:14 ^aPs 104:34 ^bPs 18:2 ^cPs 31:5; Is 47:4</p>
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Targum

¹ For praise; a psalm of David. ² Those who behold, the heavens tell of the glory of the LORD; those who gaze at the sky recount the works of his hands. ³ Day to day tells more of the word; but night to night tells less knowledge. ⁴ There is no utterance of complaint, and there are no words of confusion, for their voice is not heard. ⁵ The line of their conversation reaches through the whole earth, and their words to the end of the world. In them [the heavens] he placed a splendid dwelling for the sun. ⁶ And he, in the morning, when he comes forth, will come forth like a groom who comes out of his canopy, and in splendor will rejoice like a warrior to run the course. ⁷ His rising is at the ends of the earth, and his might reaches to all their edges; and there is none who can hide from his heat. ⁸ The Torah of the LORD is perfect, restoring the soul; the testimony of the LORD is reliable, making wise the fool. ⁹ The commands of the LORD are upright, gladdening the heart; the command of the LORD is bright, enlightening the eyes. ¹⁰ The fear of the LORD is pure, lasting forever; the judgments of the LORD are faithfulness; they are altogether just. ¹¹ More desirable than gold or than much fine gold; and more pleasant than honey or the sweet honeycombs. ¹² Truly, your servant has been careful for them, to observe them; because of this, he was made ruler of Israel. ¹³ Who knows unwitting sins? And from secret faults make me innocent. ¹⁴ Truly, from the arrogant deliver your servant, that they may not rule over me; then I will be without blemish, and I will be innocent of great sin. ¹⁵ Let the utterances of my mouth and the thought of my mind be acceptable in your presence, O LORD, my strength and my redeemer.

Spiritual Analysis

The spiritual rewrites for the verses are in bold.

Introduction to the Psalm

The psalmist refers to the flawless precision in the sky as the manifestation of the infinite wisdom and power of the Creation. Even with all its flawlessness to fully reveal the LORD, the Torah must be studied. The sage Malbim said that a diligent scholar who is on a quest for the LORD would be assisted by a holy spirit that resembles a prophecy. The psalmist offers six ways that the comprehension of the LORD is gained through Torah scholarship. The Torah also revealed how sin warped humans, and only Torah study can make humanity right once again.

Superscript (verse zero)

To the Sefirah Netzach who offers me victory.

Verse One

David says that any person who examines the nature of Heaven and Earth will know that there is a God. Heaven, especially the expanse, is flawless. The stars and planets move in patterns that never differ. Ancient people believed that the LORD was sending them a message when something different occurs, like a comet. Without light pollution, ancient people were able to see more of the sky at night. The connection between the firmament and the Torah is that the Torah was the blueprint of the Universe. Thus to understand the firmament, the Torah must be studied.

The firmament tells us about the works of the LORD, and the expanse (the stars and planet) show us His creation.

Verse Two

The daytime is when the glory of the LORD is expressed. During the night, new understandings and learnings about the LORD occur. The night reveals the quasi-Sefirot Da'at because the knowledge of the Godhead is revealed.

לַיְלָה לַיְלָה לַיְלָה (lay'la l'layla) – “night to night.” This phrase emphasizes the idea that knowledge received from Da'at in the evening is added to every night. An old set of sayings are: "rise and serve the Word," and the other is "lie down in peace; there Da'at watches over you."

Day by day I hear speech, and night by night reveals Da'at

Verse three

The day itself cannot talk. The psalmist is saying the day exists, and we can learn about the LORD in it.

There is no talk, nor words; you cannot hear the voice of the day

Verse four

The measuring line refers to laying out a measuring line to stake off territory for a purpose. In this case, the heavens assign and set the bounds for the development of every creature on the Earth. It was believed that a chariot pulled the sun across the sky (this idea is strongly expressed in 1 Enoch). The line could be where the horizon meets the Earth. The sun was pulled in its chariot from one horizon to the opposite. When the sun went down, the people believed it was placed in a tent until the next day.

The measuring line defines the horizons, where the world of man begins and ends; in this space, their words speak. The LORD has set up a tent for the sun to rest when it is not shining on the Earth.

Verse five & six

Like a bridegroom implies that the sun rejoices when it comes "out" every day, it has tremendous power, but it cannot choose its own point of origin or its orbit. The Holy Scriptures guide humans to the fulfillment of life's tasks within the framework of the constellation of existence that the LORD established.

The sun is like a bridegroom ready to be wed; the sun rejoices about its power, but it must follow the course established for it.

Even with such power, the sun must stay in its designated place in the Heavens and complete its orbit that the LORD has determined for it.

Verse 7

The psalmist turns to the Torah. If humans keep their concerns on spirituality, they will better understand the language of Heaven and Earth and its place in the world which the LORD rules. The divine Law, written in the Torah, controls the Universe. Since the LORD wrote the Torah, it is the LORD's words that control everything.

The Torah is all-encompassing and will respond to the human soul; the LORD is faithful and brings wisdom to the inexperienced person.

Verse Eight

The LORD has given humans several mandates: orders and obligations on living in the terrestrial world. The mandates are given to humans to help us live properly and enter relationships with the LORD and each other. They are not laws to hinder humanity but rather laws to free us to live a life worthy to the LORD.

The mandates of the LORD are for us to live well; the mandates rejoice the heart because the commandment of the LORD is brilliant and enlightening to the eyes.

The mandates of the LORD are upright; they cause the heart to rejoice because the commandments are brilliant and enlightening to the eyes.

Verse Nine

The English translation uses the word "fear." This word can be translated as "reverence." If one enters the LORD's presence, a sense of reverence and fear should come to the person immediately. The acts of Gevurah (judgment) are given to humanity to help humanity learn the ways of the LORD as defined in the Torah. The consequences can be viewed as a punishment or a correction To the society's norms of the day.

Reverence of the LORD is pure and endures forever; Gevurah consistently demonstrates mercy and tolerance. Sometimes the judgment from Gevurah seems harsh, but it is that way to teach the people a needed-to-know lesson.

Have pure reverence of the LORD; enduring forever, because the ways of Geruvah always have a touch of Chesed.

Verse 10

For the spiritually-minded person, the treasures of Heaven are far more critical than the treasures of the Earth. Humans tend to want an accumulation of materialism, and they use this material to show other people their worth. That may work fine on the planet; however, in Heaven these material objects do not exist. Therefore which is more important to collect, spiritual treasures or earthly treasures?

The purity of the LORD is more desirable than gold and the finest gems, definitely sweeter than honey or the finest nectar.

Verse 11

David knew that the Laws of the LORD restrained him from doing some things that he wanted to do. As he gained wisdom, he realized that it was best to follow the Law than his carnal instincts.

Your servant knew of your Laws, and by keeping them, he recognized the rich rewards.

Verse 12

David was concerned about the errors that he committed because he did not have a perfect understanding of what the LORD expected of him

Who can discern errors? Who cleans me from hidden faults.

Verse 13

David asked the LORD to protect him from errors he made because of his lack of understanding and those errors created by the evil principles of depraved men who might influence him in times of weaknesses.

Prevent your servant from committing sins so the sins do not rule over me; then I will be blameless and innocent of sins.

Verse 14

David asks the LORD to listen to him and give him His attention.

May the words I speak, and the meditation of my heart find favor before You, my rock and my Redeemer.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

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There is no talk, nor words; you cannot hear the voice of the day

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The purity of the LORD is more desirable than gold and the finest gems, definitely sweeter than honey or the finest nectar.

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Who can discern errors? Who cleans me from hidden faults.

Prevent your servant from committing sins so the acts do not rule over me; then I will be blameless and innocent of sins.

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Appendix

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Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

